

Astrometric precision of GAIA

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1 Introduction

This note gives estimates of the astrometric precision of GAIA as a function of magnitude and colour. It is based on the method described in the GAIA Payload Definition Document [1], using optical and detector characteristics essentially as specified by MMS in January 1998 [2]. The estimates contain realistic assumptions on all the degrading effects that are considered (as detailed in Section 2), but no additional error margin is included.

2 Assumptions

2.1 Stellar fluxes

The relative energy distribution in various (real) stellar spectra were taken from a standard stellar spectrophotometric atlas [3]. For the present study 16 (dereddened) spectra were selected to cover most of the main sequence and a few giants (see Tables 2 and 3). The relative fluxes (in energy per frequency interval) were converted to absolute fluxes (in $\text{ph m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{nm}^{-1}$) for apparent magnitude $V = 0$ through multiplication by C/λ , where C is a constant determined for each spectrum by means of the conditions:

1. for an unreddened star of spectral type A0V and $V = 0$ the energy flux at $\lambda = 550 \text{ nm}$ should be $3.66 \times 10^{-11} \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ nm}^{-1}$ ([4], Table 21), corresponding to $1.0133 \times 10^8 \text{ ph m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ nm}^{-1}$;
2. for other spectral types and for reddened stars, C is adjusted to give the same wavelength-integrated energy flux (not photon flux) as the unreddened A0V star, when weighted by the V band sensitivity curve in [5] (Table AII).

Using the sensitivity curves in [5] for the (Cousins) R and I bands, the R and I magnitudes of the stars can also be obtained, using that $V - R = -0.01$ and $V - I = -0.02$ for the unreddened A0V star ([4], Table 27).

For application of interstellar extinction the curve in [4] (Table 3) is used, with linear interpolation in $1/\lambda$.

2.2 Sky background

A value of $V = 21.0$ per arcsec^2 is assumed, and the colour is taken to be $V - I = 0.7$.

2.3 Mission parameters

The assumed spin rate is $120 \text{ arcsec s}^{-1}$. Revolving scanning is assumed with Sun/spin axis angle $\xi = 55^\circ$.

The mission length is $L = 5 \text{ yr}$, including a total dead time of 1 yr (20 per cent) for attitude and orbit manoeuvres and similar. Thus the total time available for observations is 4 yr.

2.4 Optics

Two interferometers are assumed, each with a rectangular pupil of $1.7 \times 0.7 \text{ m}^2$. In the software the telescope was represented by an interferometer with two rectangular pupils of width $D = 0.85 \text{ m}$ and baseline $B = 0.85 \text{ m}$. However, separate calculations were made to verify that the total flux and polychromatic optical PSF obtained with this software did indeed match those a single rectangular pupil.

The focal length is 50 m and the optical transmittance 0.9 at all wavelengths.

Aberrations are assumed to give a Strehl ratio of 0.8 at $\lambda = 500 \text{ nm}$. This corresponds to an rms wavefront error of $W = 37.6 \text{ nm}$. The aberrations are taken into account through scaling down the monochromatic PSF by the Strehl ratio as function of wavelength, $\exp[-(2\pi W/\lambda)^2]$, but without changing the form or width of the PSF.

2.5 CCD detectors

The quantum efficiency is taken from the curve for CCD#3 in the MMS report [2], here reproduced as Table 1. The CCD mosaic used for astrometry consists of 124 subarrays in each interferometer. Each subarray contains 2502 pixels of $9 \mu\text{m}$ pitch along scan, and 1920 pixels of $30 \mu\text{m}$ pitch normal to the scan. The 2502 pixels along scan are 90 per cent of the 2780 pixels in the MMS report; the remaining 10 per cent may be dedicated to observing bright stars (to avoid saturation) and are therefore not included here.

It is assumed that 4 pixels in the transverse direction are added on-chip before readout. The width of this logical pixel ($120 \mu\text{m}$) nearly matches the full width of the diffraction image normal to the scan, between the first minima. Since the diffraction normal to the scan is not formally included in the basic estimation method, it is instead assumed that only 90 per cent of the light falls within the logical pixel. The readout noise is 5 electrons rms.

The electronic MTF is modelled by the exponential charge diffusion model proposed in [1], with lateral diffusion ($1/e$) length $d = 1.2 \mu\text{m}$. For $9 \mu\text{m}$ pixel width this corresponds to an electronic MTF of 0.85 at the Nyquist frequency, or $0.85 \times (2/\pi) \simeq 0.54$ in the total (electronic + sampling) MTF.

Table 1. Assumed quantum efficiency of CCD detectors (CCD#3). Linear interpolation is used between the tabulated values.

λ	Q_λ	λ	Q_λ	λ	Q_λ	λ	Q_λ
300	0.00	500	0.77	700	0.91	900	0.55
350	0.05	550	0.82	750	0.84	950	0.38
400	0.21	600	0.90	800	0.77	1000	0.20
450	0.60	650	0.91	850	0.66	1050	0.00

2.6 Distortion and attitude errors

The total TDI error resulting from differential distortion within a single CCD subarray and from attitude errors is set to 0.3 pixel rms (assumed to be Gaussian). This affects the error assessment only through a statistical degradation of the MTF (PSF smearing).

2.7 Image location process

In [1] an analytical approximation of the Cramér-Rao bound was used to estimate the precision of the image location process in the presence of photon and readout noise. This approximation contains an empirical constant k which was conservatively set to 0.5 in [1]. For the present assessment this constant was calibrated anew by means of dedicated Monte Carlo simulations.

For each of 12 different spectral type/magnitude combinations, the rms location error was calculated from 60 000 experiments, in which the true location was uniformly distributed over a pixel. The location process used the readout values (n_j) from 5 pixels ($j = 1 \dots 5$), where the middle one contained the actual centre of the PSF. The location was found by maximizing

$$c(x) = \sum_{j=1}^5 [n_j \ln S_j(x) - S_j(x)] \quad (1)$$

where $S_j(x) = \beta + \alpha P(j - x)$ is the expectation of n_j if the PSF is centred on x (the along-scan coordinate of the image measured in pixels). α and β are the intensities of the star and background (assumed to be known). The PSF was calculated in steps of 1/8 pixel and the maximum of $c(x)$ was found by first locating it to the nearest step of 1/8 pixel and then making a parabolic fit, using also the two adjacent steps, to refine the estimate.

Incidentally, it was found that this procedure gave no significant bias as function of sub-pixel position, and that the precision of the location was also practically independent of the position. Using 7 pixels instead of 5 would only give a very marginal improvement ($\simeq -1$ per cent in the standard error), while 3 pixels would deteriorate the results significantly (by +13 to 26 per cent). The location process failed (i.e., no maximum was found within ± 1 pixel of the expected centre) in only 12 of the 720 000 experiments; all of the failures occurred at $V = 21$.

Comparing the rms errors found from these experiments with the analytical formula for different values of k , it was found that the analytical formula could reproduce the simulation results with k ranging from 0.32 (for $V \leq 15$) to 0.25 (for $V \sim 21$). For the following assessment the analytical approximation was used, assuming $k = 0.32$. For bright stars this gives practically the same results as the Monte Carlo simulations, while for faint stars it overestimates the standard error by some 4 per cent at $V = 20$ and up to 11 per cent for blue stars at $V = 21$.

2.8 Calibration, attitude and metrology

The location measurements in pixel coordinates need to be transformed to angular field coordinates through a geometrical calibration of the focal plane, and subsequently to coordinates on the sky through calibrations of the instrument attitude and basic angle metrology. No complete model exists for this part of the accuracy analysis. It can be assumed that these errors are negligible for faint stars, where photon, readout and background (including crowding) noise will dominate. But for very bright stars they will probably be the limiting factor.

Lacking a better model, it is assumed that the contribution from these errors is equivalent to the total weight of location measurements between $V = 12$ and 20 obtained in 0.77 s (one subarray crossing) in a single field of view pointing to the Galactic pole. This gives then a constant contribution $\sigma_0 \simeq 25 \mu\text{as}$ (6 nm) to the standard error of the location process.

2.9 Propagation to parallax and proper motion

The geometrical factor G_π relating the scanning geometry to the determination of parallaxes is set to

$$G_\pi = 1.64(\sin \xi)^{-1} \quad (2)$$

corresponding to $G_\pi = 2$ for $\xi = 55^\circ$. For proper motions the factor is

$$G_\mu = 6.0L^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where $L = 5.0$ is the mission length in years. G_μ is practically independent of ξ , if the mean precision in ecliptic longitude and latitude is considered.

3 Results

Results for the estimated precision in parallax and proper motion are given in Tables 2 and 3. It is found that the precision is nearly a unique function of the magnitude

$$m = V - 0.360(V-I) - 0.087(V-I)^2. \quad (4)$$

The tables can therefore be approximated (to within ~ 3 per cent) by the expressions

$$\sigma_{\pi}^2 = 1.50 \mu\text{as}^2 + 10^{0.4(m-9.67)} \times [1 + 10^{0.4(m-20.0)}] \quad (5)$$

and

$$\sigma_{\mu} = 0.6\sigma_{\pi}. \quad (6)$$

4 Comparison with MMS results

The number of detected photons per second is given in [2] as 31470, 40460 and 250339 for spectral types B3V, G2V and M8V. In the present assessment the numbers are: 33454 (for B1V), 45665, and 268220, or 6 to 13 per cent larger. The reason for this discrepancy is under investigation.

The optical PSFs calculated here are very similar to those in [2]: MMS gives a FWHM of 1.59 and 2.30 pixels for B3V and M8V, respectively, while the present values are 1.54 (B1V) and 2.30 (M8V). The global PSFs (i.e. including pixel and TDI smearing) are also in good agreement.

Concerning other assumptions it can be noted that the present assessment makes a more pessimistic assumption concerning the available detector area for faint stars (MMS: 0.27 deg^2 ; here: 0.21 deg^2). Other assumptions (aberrations, MTF, TDI errors) are practically equivalent.

As a result of these differences one expects that the present error estimates should be about 10 per cent higher than those of MMS. MMS finds, for $V = 15$ and spectral types B3V, G2V and K8V $\sigma_{\pi} = 9.7, 9.3$ and $4.2 \mu\text{as}$, while the present assessment gives 11.6 (B1V), 10.6 and $5.0 \mu\text{as}$. The latter values are in fact 15 to 20 per cent greater than the MMS estimates, a somewhat larger difference than expected.

References

1. GAIA Payload Definition Document, Annex A (draft, Sept. 1997)
2. GAIA Concept and Technology Study: Mid-Term Presentation (GAIA/MMS/HO/018.98), 14 January 1998
3. Gunn J.E., Stryker L.L., *Stellar spectrophotometric atlas*, $3130 < \lambda < 10800 \text{ \AA}$, *Astrophys. J. Suppl. Ser.* 52, 121, 1983
4. Straižys V., *Multicolor stellar photometry*, Pachart Publ. House (Tucson) 1992
5. Bessell M.S., *VRI photometry: An addendum*, *Publ. Astron. Soc. Pacific* 95, 480, 1983

Table 2. Estimated precision in parallax (σ_π , in μas) as a function of spectral type (or colours), reddening (A_V) and V magnitude.

Sp	A_V	$V-R$	$V-I$	$V =$											
				10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
B1V	0.0	-0.16	-0.33	1.68	2.19	3.13	4.73	7.35	11.6	18.5	29.8	49.4	86.4	165.	349.
A0V	0.0	-0.01	-0.02	1.68	2.19	3.13	4.72	7.34	11.6	18.4	29.7	49.2	85.8	163.	344.
A3V	0.0	0.01	0.02	1.68	2.19	3.13	4.73	7.35	11.6	18.5	29.8	49.3	85.9	163.	344.
A5V	0.0	0.13	0.27	1.66	2.15	3.06	4.62	7.17	11.3	18.0	28.9	47.7	82.9	156.	327.
F2V	0.0	0.19	0.36	1.65	2.13	3.03	4.56	7.08	11.1	17.7	28.5	47.0	81.4	153.	319.
F6V	0.0	0.25	0.51	1.63	2.10	2.98	4.47	6.93	10.9	17.3	27.9	45.9	79.1	148.	306.
F8V	0.0	0.31	0.60	1.62	2.08	2.93	4.40	6.81	10.7	17.0	27.4	45.0	77.3	144.	297.
G2V	0.0	0.35	0.70	1.61	2.06	2.90	4.34	6.72	10.6	16.8	26.9	44.2	75.9	141.	289.
K3V	0.0	0.54	0.98	1.57	1.98	2.75	4.09	6.31	9.91	15.7	25.2	41.2	70.0	128.	258.
M0V	0.0	0.93	1.74	1.46	1.76	2.35	3.40	5.18	8.08	12.8	20.3	32.8	54.6	95.8	184.
M8V	0.0	1.37	3.14	1.32	1.44	1.72	2.27	3.27	4.96	7.72	12.2	19.4	31.2	51.6	89.5
G8III	0.0	0.51	0.96	1.58	1.99	2.78	4.14	6.39	10.0	15.9	25.5	41.7	71.0	130.	263.
K3III	0.0	0.72	1.33	1.52	1.88	2.57	3.78	5.80	9.08	14.4	23.0	37.3	62.8	113.	222.
M0III	0.0	0.88	1.70	1.47	1.77	2.36	3.43	5.23	8.16	12.9	20.5	33.2	55.2	97.0	186.
M7III	0.0	2.23	4.54	1.25	1.28	1.36	1.53	1.90	2.62	3.86	5.94	9.31	14.7	23.5	38.2
B0Ib	0.0	-0.14	-0.33	1.68	2.19	3.13	4.73	7.35	11.6	18.5	29.8	49.4	86.3	165.	348.
B1V	5.0	0.83	1.66	1.47	1.78	2.38	3.46	5.28	8.24	13.0	20.7	33.5	55.8	98.2	189.
A0V	5.0	0.98	1.94	1.43	1.69	2.21	3.16	4.77	7.42	11.7	18.6	29.9	49.4	85.4	160.
A3V	5.0	0.99	1.98	1.42	1.68	2.19	3.13	4.72	7.34	11.6	18.4	29.6	48.7	84.1	158.
A5V	5.0	1.12	2.22	1.39	1.61	2.06	2.91	4.35	6.74	10.6	16.8	27.0	44.2	75.4	139.
F2V	5.0	1.18	2.30	1.38	1.59	2.02	2.83	4.23	6.53	10.3	16.3	26.1	42.6	72.5	132.
F6V	5.0	1.26	2.45	1.37	1.56	1.96	2.72	4.04	6.23	9.77	15.5	24.8	40.4	68.2	123.
F8V	5.0	1.31	2.53	1.36	1.54	1.91	2.63	3.89	5.98	9.38	14.8	23.7	38.6	64.9	116.
G2V	5.0	1.36	2.62	1.35	1.52	1.88	2.56	3.78	5.80	9.08	14.4	22.9	37.2	62.4	111.
K3V	5.0	1.53	2.86	1.33	1.47	1.77	2.37	3.43	5.23	8.17	12.9	20.5	33.2	55.0	96.4
M0V	5.0	1.92	3.56	1.28	1.36	1.55	1.94	2.69	3.98	6.13	9.62	15.2	24.4	39.6	66.8
M8V	5.0	2.63	5.01	1.24	1.26	1.31	1.43	1.69	2.22	3.19	4.82	7.50	11.8	18.8	30.2
G8III	5.0	1.50	2.85	1.33	1.47	1.78	2.38	3.45	5.26	8.21	13.0	20.7	33.4	55.4	97.2
K3III	5.0	1.72	3.19	1.30	1.41	1.65	2.13	3.02	4.55	7.06	11.1	17.6	28.3	46.5	79.7
M0III	5.0	1.89	3.54	1.28	1.36	1.54	1.92	2.65	3.93	6.04	9.47	15.0	24.0	39.0	65.5
M7III	5.0	3.62	6.37	1.23	1.23	1.24	1.27	1.33	1.48	1.79	2.41	3.50	5.35	8.35	13.2
B0Ib	5.0	0.83	1.65	1.47	1.77	2.37	3.44	5.25	8.19	12.9	20.6	33.3	55.4	97.4	187.

Table 3. Estimated precision in proper motion (σ_μ , in $\mu\text{as yr}^{-1}$) as a function of spectral type (or colours), reddening (A_V) and V magnitude.

Sp	A_V	$V-R$	$V-I$	$V =$											
				10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
B1V	0.0	-0.16	-0.33	1.01	1.31	1.88	2.84	4.41	6.95	11.1	17.9	29.6	51.8	98.8	209.
A0V	0.0	-0.01	-0.02	1.00	1.31	1.87	2.83	4.40	6.94	11.0	17.8	29.5	51.4	97.8	206.
A3V	0.0	0.01	0.02	1.01	1.31	1.88	2.84	4.41	6.95	11.1	17.8	29.5	51.5	97.9	206.
A5V	0.0	0.13	0.27	0.99	1.29	1.84	2.77	4.30	6.77	10.8	17.3	28.6	49.7	93.7	196.
F2V	0.0	0.19	0.36	0.99	1.28	1.82	2.73	4.24	6.68	10.6	17.1	28.2	48.8	91.7	191.
F6V	0.0	0.25	0.51	0.98	1.26	1.78	2.68	4.15	6.54	10.4	16.7	27.5	47.4	88.7	184.
F8V	0.0	0.31	0.60	0.97	1.25	1.76	2.64	4.08	6.42	10.2	16.4	26.9	46.3	86.3	178.
G2V	0.0	0.35	0.70	0.96	1.23	1.74	2.60	4.02	6.33	10.1	16.1	26.5	45.5	84.3	173.
K3V	0.0	0.54	0.98	0.94	1.19	1.65	2.45	3.78	5.94	9.42	15.1	24.7	41.9	76.7	155.
M0V	0.0	0.93	1.74	0.88	1.05	1.41	2.04	3.10	4.84	7.64	12.2	19.7	32.7	57.4	110.
M8V	0.0	1.37	3.14	0.79	0.86	1.03	1.36	1.96	2.97	4.63	7.30	11.6	18.7	30.9	53.6
G8III	0.0	0.51	0.96	0.94	1.19	1.66	2.48	3.83	6.01	9.54	15.3	25.0	42.6	78.0	158.
K3III	0.0	0.72	1.33	0.91	1.12	1.54	2.26	3.48	5.44	8.62	13.8	22.4	37.6	67.5	133.
M0III	0.0	0.88	1.70	0.88	1.06	1.42	2.06	3.13	4.89	7.72	12.3	19.9	33.1	58.1	112.
M7III	0.0	2.23	4.54	0.75	0.77	0.81	0.92	1.14	1.57	2.32	3.56	5.58	8.83	14.1	22.9
B0Ib	0.0	-0.14	-0.33	1.01	1.31	1.88	2.84	4.41	6.95	11.1	17.8	29.6	51.7	98.7	209.
B1V	5.0	0.83	1.66	0.88	1.07	1.43	2.07	3.16	4.94	7.80	12.4	20.1	33.4	58.9	113.
A0V	5.0	0.98	1.94	0.85	1.01	1.32	1.89	2.86	4.45	7.01	11.2	17.9	29.6	51.2	96.2
A3V	5.0	0.99	1.98	0.85	1.00	1.31	1.87	2.83	4.40	6.93	11.0	17.7	29.2	50.4	94.4
A5V	5.0	1.12	2.22	0.83	0.97	1.24	1.74	2.61	4.04	6.35	10.1	16.2	26.5	45.2	83.0
F2V	5.0	1.18	2.30	0.83	0.95	1.21	1.70	2.53	3.92	6.15	9.76	15.6	25.6	43.4	79.3
F6V	5.0	1.26	2.45	0.82	0.94	1.18	1.63	2.42	3.73	5.86	9.28	14.9	24.2	40.9	74.0
F8V	5.0	1.31	2.53	0.81	0.92	1.15	1.58	2.33	3.59	5.62	8.90	14.2	23.1	38.9	69.8
G2V	5.0	1.36	2.62	0.81	0.91	1.12	1.54	2.26	3.47	5.44	8.61	13.7	22.3	37.4	66.7
K3V	5.0	1.53	2.86	0.79	0.88	1.06	1.42	2.06	3.14	4.89	7.73	12.3	19.9	33.0	57.8
M0V	5.0	1.92	3.56	0.77	0.82	0.93	1.16	1.61	2.39	3.68	5.77	9.13	14.6	23.8	40.0
M8V	5.0	2.63	5.01	0.74	0.76	0.79	0.86	1.02	1.33	1.91	2.89	4.50	7.09	11.3	18.1
G8III	5.0	1.50	2.85	0.80	0.88	1.06	1.42	2.07	3.15	4.92	7.78	12.4	20.0	33.2	58.2
K3III	5.0	1.72	3.19	0.78	0.84	0.99	1.28	1.81	2.73	4.23	6.66	10.6	17.0	27.9	47.7
M0III	5.0	1.89	3.54	0.77	0.82	0.92	1.15	1.59	2.35	3.62	5.68	8.99	14.4	23.3	39.2
M7III	5.0	3.62	6.37	0.74	0.74	0.74	0.76	0.80	0.89	1.07	1.44	2.10	3.21	5.01	7.91
B0Ib	5.0	0.83	1.65	0.88	1.06	1.42	2.06	3.15	4.91	7.75	12.4	20.0	33.2	58.4	112.